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Metabarcoding protocol: Pooling and Library Preparation for sequencing

This setup is for sequencing amplicons on ILLUMINA platforms

NB always use in combination with the metabarcoding library preparation. Checklist.

- 1) After the PCR get someone to pack your plates in 2 plastic bags, and pass it to you in the semi-clean library preparation lab.
- 2) Throw away the outer bag and clean with bleach the inner bag around your samples.
- 3) Put your samples in the fridge (if not working straight away) otherwise place on the lab bench to equilibrate to room temperature while you clean the hoods and equipment following the protocol.
- 4) Take necessary chemicals out of the freezer 30 mins prior to work to defrost. This takes approx. the same time as UV'ing the hood after cleaning, so do this simultaneously.
 - a. Ampure beads
 - b. ETOH (in freezer)
 - c. Water (fridge)
 - d. Standards for qubit BR

Pooling and min elute

1. For each plate use a multichannel pipette to pool 15 microliters of each sample into an eight-well strip.
2. Combine the 8 well strip into an 1.5ML LOBIND eppendorf tube, label this with the plate name, marker (e.g. COI, 12S), pre-pool, your name and the date.
3. For each pool make 6 new eppendorf tubes, each with 125microL of the pool and add 625microL of PB buffer (minelute kit).
4. Vortex and briefly spin down the 6 tubes.
5. Prepare 3 minelute spin columns, and add the 750microL sample PB buffer mix to these columns.
6. Spin the column at 13 RPM for 1 minute
7. Throw away the flowthrough and then add the remaining 3 tubes of sample PB mix to these 3 minelute columns.
8. Spin the column at 13 RPM for 1 minute
9. Throw away the flowthrough and then add 750 microL of PE buffer to the columns
10. Spin the column at 13 RPM for 1 minute
11. Throw away the flowthrough
12. Spin the column at 13 RPM for 1 minute
13. Add 15microL of EB buffer to each column making sure that it only touches the filter.
14. Spin the column at 13 RPM for 1 minute

- Combine the 3 tubes with 15 microliters into one DNA lo-bind tube and label with the plate name, marker (e.g. COI, 12S), post-pool, your name and the date.

Quantification

- Make a qubit Broad range master mix by combining 1 microliter dye with 99 microliter buffer for $x = n+2$ samples ($n = \text{number of samples} + \text{number of standards}$)
 - e.g. 10 samples $n=12$ $x= 14$
 - Dye = 14 micro L. Buffer = 2786 microL
- Add 198 microL of master mix (MM) to 10 sample tubes and 190 microL of MM to 2 standard tubes.
- Add 2 microL of each plate post pool to each qubit sample tube.
- Add 10 microL of each standard to each qubit standard tube.
- Start up the qubit fluorometer , select dsDNA broad range and measure the standards first then the samples.

Library preparation

This protocol is modified for the Qiaseq one step amplicon library preparation kit

Cleanup = Ampure beads (BIOO method)

Start DNA concentration 3000 ng

- Prepare either an 8 well strip or plate dependent on the number of libraries to prepare.
- Combine the following in each well:

Component	Volume/reaction (microL)
DNA (post pool minelute) 3000ng	X
water	31.5-X
4x 1-step Library Buffer	12.5
Y adapter	4
1-step Amplicon enzyme mix	2
Total	50

- Set pipete to 20-30 microL mix the components by pipetting up and down 10 times
- Program a thermal cycler to incubate at 25C for 1 hour.

Cleanup

Cleanup BIOO PCR free 30 minutes

- Measure each sample using a 100microL pipette set to 50 microL
- Make sample up to 54.5 microL with H₂O
- Add 44 microL beads and pipette up and down 10 times to mix

4. wait 5 minutes
5. Place the tubes on the magnetic rack for 2 minutes
6. Remove and discard supernatant
7. Wash 2 x with 80% ETOH (freshly prepared) 200 microL
8. Dry 3-5 mins
9. Resuspend with 57microL resuspension buffer
10. Wait 2 mins, place on stand and transfer supernatant to a clean tube 54.5 microL
11. Add 44 microL of beads
12. Incubate 5 minutes then place on magnet
13. Remove supernatant and discard
14. Wash 2 x with 80% ETOH
15. Dry 3-5 mins
16. Add 22.5 MicroL resuspension buffer
17. Incubate 2 minutes
18. Place on a magnet for 5 minutes
19. Transfer 20 microL of library
- 20.